

HexNet: Multi-modal Fusion of Panchromatic Imagery and Temporal NDVI Data for Historical Dryland Tree Crown Segmentation

Toon Lambrecht*, Deniz Soysal*, Ben Somers*, and Stef Lhermitte*

*Division of Forest, Nature and Landscape, KU Leuven, Belgium ,
toon.lambrecht@kuleuven.be, deniz.soysal@kuleuven.be, ben.somers@kuleuven.be,
stef.lhermitte@kuleuven.be

Abstract

Long-term, high-resolution assessments of dryland woody vegetation remain scarce due to limited historical remote-sensing data. Declassified Hexagon KH-9 panchromatic imagery offers unique spatial detail but lacks spectral information and poses processing challenges. We present HexNet, a scalable multi-modal deep learning (DL) framework that integrates high-resolution panchromatic imagery with coarse temporal vegetation signals to improve tree crown delineation under historical data constraints. Using simulated historical data derived from multiple National Ecological Observatory Network (NEON) sites, we benchmark HexNet against spatial-only deep learning baselines across gradients of tree density. HexNet increases precision by +2 percentage points overall (0.85 vs 0.83 for the best spatial-only baseline) while maintaining comparable recall (0.87). Gains are strongest in sparsely vegetated tiles ($< 10\%$ tree cover), where precision improves by +8 percentage points (0.56 vs 0.48). These results highlight the potential of our approach for long-term dryland ecosystem analysis using high resolution panchromatic archives.

Keywords: Dryland Monitoring, Multi-Modal Deep Learning, Historical Satellite Imagery

1. Introduction

Dryland trees and shrubs are key components of terrestrial carbon storage, biodiversity conservation, and rural livelihoods (Stringer et al. 2012). Recent advances in very high resolution (VHR) satellite imagery and deep learning have enabled individual tree mapping and fine scale analyses of vegetation structure and dynamics (Brandt et al. 2020). However, long term assessments of dryland woody vegetation at comparable spatial resolution remain scarce, primarily due to the lack of suitable historical remote sensing data.

Published in “Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Geospatial Artificial Intelligence (GeoAI 2026) – Oral Presentation Papers”, edited by Haosheng Huang and Nico Van de Weghe, GeoAI 2026, 3-6 June 2026, Ghent, Belgium.

This contribution underwent single-blind peer review based on the extended abstract.

Declassified Cold War reconnaissance imagery, particularly from the Hexagon KH-9 Panoramic Camera System (1971–1984), provides a unique historical archive with ground resolutions of approximately 0.6–1.2 m. While these data offer high spatial detail, their use is hindered by geometric distortions, limited metadata, and the absence of multispectral information (Marzloff et al. 2022). These constraints are especially limiting in dryland environments, where sparse vegetation, herbaceous plants and shrubs complicate tree detection. Consequently, previous dryland studies using such imagery have remained small scale, relying on manual interpretation or traditional image processing techniques that limit scalability (Dendoncker et al. 2020; Brandt et al. 2014; Spiekermann, Brandt, and Samimi 2015).

In this paper, we investigate whether coarse temporal vegetation signals can compensate for the lack of multispectral information in historical panchromatic imagery to enable scalable dryland tree crown delineation. To test this, we introduce HexNet, a lightweight multi-modal framework that fuses 1m panchromatic imagery with a monthly NDVI time series at 128m resolution. We evaluate HexNet on a controlled “historical-like” simulation benchmark using data retrieved from NEON sites, a network of U.S. ecological field sites providing standardized, open airborne and in-situ observations. We then quantify performance across gradients of tree density.

2. Methods

Our methodology consists of (i) generating panchromatic, “historical-like” image tiles and corresponding crown masks from NEON airborne products, (ii) associating each tile with a monthly NDVI time series representing seasonal vegetation dynamics, and (iii) benchmarking a multi-modal fusion model against spatial-only baselines using consistent training splits and standard segmentation metrics.

2.1. Data

We retrieved airborne RGB orthomosaics and canopy height models (CHMs) from five NEON sites (CLBJ, MOAB, PRIN, SJER, and SRER), spanning a broad gradient of woody cover and vegetation structure—from the cactus-dominated Sonoran Desert (SRER) to the oak–grassland mosaics of the Caddo–Lyndon B. Johnson National Grasslands (CLBJ) (NEON 2026). By sampling multiple ecosystem types, we benchmark model performance across different woody cover regimes. Furthermore, the sparsely vegetated subsets constitute dryland environments and provide a relevant test set for evaluating tree crown delineation under low tree-density semi-arid conditions. The retrieved orthomosaics were downsampled to a ground sampling distance (GSD) of 1 m to match KH-9 satellite imagery. RGB imagery was converted to panchromatic format using a linear combination of the 3 bands. To emulate artifacts characteristic of historical satellite and aerial imagery, we applied contrast-limited adaptive histogram equalization (CLAHE), directional motion blur, reduced sharpness, and synthetic film grain and noise (Marzloff et al. 2022; Shahtahmasebi et al. 2023). The processed data were tiled into 128×128 pixel tiles ($128m \times 128m$, at 1m GSD) with one-third overlap and split into geographically disjoint training, validation, and test sets (70/20/10). In total, we obtained 101 741 tiles. The CHMs were used to generate ground-truth tree crown masks through height filtering (retaining pixels exceeding 3 m), NDVI thresholding, and additional site-specific image-processing steps to ensure consistency.

For each site, Landsat 8 imagery covering the 12 months preceding NEON acquisition was retrieved, cloud-masked, and averaged monthly to derive NDVI time series. Missing values were filled via cubic interpolation, and an $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 12}$ NDVI vector was obtained by spatially averaging the NDVI values per panchromatic tile. In a real integration scenario with historical data, earlier Landsat missions would need to be used. Therefore, this tile-level aggregation reflects the coarse early-Landsat resolution (80 m) and potential georeferencing uncertainty, constituting a conservative, worst-case integration scenario (Wulder et al. 2022).

2.2 HexNet: Spatio-temporal Fusion Architecture

To support scalable tree-crown segmentation and mitigate the lack of spectral information in historical panchromatic imagery, we developed HexNet, a lightweight multi-modal architecture that fuses fine-scale panchromatic texture with a coarse monthly NDVI time series. The NDVI branch provides complementary seasonal information that helps the model distinguish woody vegetation from spectrally ambiguous background patterns. The current version outputs binary crown masks using two encoder branches followed by a cross-modal fusion decoder.

The spatial encoder processes the image tiles using a small convolutional neural network (CNN) backbone, followed by a Swin Transformer. This enables both local texture extraction and long-range contextual reasoning. The temporal encoder processes the NDVI time series using a Transformer encoder, producing a compact temporal embedding that captures seasonal vegetation dynamics. Both branches are fused using cross-attention and the data is then up-sampled using 3 fusion blocks. Within each fusion block, cross attention is applied between the temporal embeddings and a skip connection from the CNN-backbone. Additionally, the embeddings from the previous layer are upsampled using Pixel Shuffle (Ibrahim, Salem, and Kang 2025). Both are concatenated and fed to the next fusion block. The final refinement head uses a shallow CNN to map high-resolution fused features to the output space with minimal additional computational overhead.

2.3 Model Training and Evaluation

Models were trained using a hybrid loss function combining Focal loss and Dice loss, enabling the optimization to address class imbalance and hard-to-classify samples while improving spatial overlap with the ground truth data (Al-Shamayleh, Qatawneh, and Elsalamony 2025). To assess the contribution of temporal information, two spatial-only baselines were trained from scratch using the same dataset: a HexNet variant without the temporal encoder (hereafter HexNet-Spatial) and a standard U-Net model (Ronneberger, Fischer, and Brox 2015). All models were trained for 50 epochs, using an AdamW optimizer and batch size of 64 with exponential learning rate decay. Model performance was evaluated using Precision, Recall, and Intersection over Union (IoU), with results stratified by tree-density classes. HexNet contains approximately 2.99 M trainable parameters, compared to 1.63 M for HexNet-Spatial and 31.03 M for U-Net. This shows that HexNet has a compact and parameter-efficient architecture. Finally, all experiments were implemented in PyTorch and executed on an NVIDIA RTX 5000 Ada Generation GPU (32 GB)

3. Results

3.1 Model Training

Training and validation loss curves for all three models are shown in Figure 1. All models have stable convergence behavior, with training and validation losses decreasing smoothly and reaching a plateau. No pronounced divergence between training and validation losses is observed, indicating that none of the models suffers from excessive overfitting.

Figure 1: Train and validation loss for the three models trained from scratch.

3.2. Model Evaluation

Table 1 shows that Recall values are comparable across all three models, indicating that each model detects a similar proportion of tree crown pixels overall. In contrast, HexNet consistently achieves higher Precision than both HexNet-Spatial and U-Net, reflecting a lower rate of false positive predictions. This advantage is also reflected in a slightly higher IoU, indicating greater spatial overlap between predicted and ground-truth tree crown maps compared to the spatial-only baselines. Performance differences become more pronounced in sparsely vegetated areas with less than 10 % tree cover (Table 1), where all models show reduced performance. While Recall remains similar across models (0.66–0.68), HexNet has a substantially higher Precision (0.56) than HexNet-Spatial (0.45) and U-Net (0.48). HexNet also achieves the highest IoU for areas with < 10% vegetation. This pattern is also visible qualitatively (Figure 2), where HexNet-Spatial and U-Net produce more false positives outside the ground-truth contours, while HexNet predictions align more closely with the reference mask.

Table 1: Performance comparison of HexNet, HexNet-Spatial, and U-Net models, using Precision (P), Recall (R), IoU for the full dataset and for areas with less than 10 % tree cover.

Model	Overall			< 10% Tree Cover		
	P	R	IoU	P	R	IoU
HexNet	0.85	0.87	0.76	0.56	0.66	0.44
HexNet-Spatial	0.82	0.87	0.75	0.45	0.67	0.37
U-Net	0.83	0.87	0.74	0.48	0.68	0.39

Figure 2: Comparison between ground truth masks and predictions by all three models. To visualize how well the predictions align, a color coding is used to show each possible combination of model predictions against the ground truth data (see legend for model encoding).

4. Discussion and Conclusion

All three models show reduced performance in sparsely vegetated areas, reflecting the difficulty of separating individual tree crowns from shrubs, herbaceous vegetation, and background texture in dryland environments. Despite these challenges, HexNet consistently achieves higher Precision than both HexNet-Spatial and U-Net, while maintaining comparable Recall. This indicates that incorporating coarse seasonal information can primarily reduce false positives. This is important in open-canopy settings where over-detection could strongly bias woody cover estimates and inflate ecological metrics.

Because these experiments use simulated “historical-like” data, transfer to true KH-9 (or other historical) imagery may be affected by geometric distortions, scanning artifacts, and domain shifts. Nonetheless, these issues could be mitigated by adapting the model to real historical scenes, for example via a small curated dataset for fine-tuning (or other lightweight domain-adaptation strategies). With such adaptations, the proposed approach has the potential to enable larger-scale case studies and broaden the scope of previous work that relied on localized patch-based or labor-intensive methodologies for quantifying historical woody cover in dryland environments (Dendoncker et al. 2020; Brandt et al. 2014; Spiekermann, Brandt, and Samimi 2015).

While the results are promising, the proposed architecture and training strategy are not finalized. Persistent misclassifications indicate that the temporal branch is not yet fully exploited, which motivates future exploration of alternative learning strategies and architectural choices to improve cross-modal integration. In addition, moving from semantic to instance segmentation would enable explicit modeling of individual trees and support more detailed analyses of tree density, structure, and long-term changes in woody cover and carbon stocks. Finally, the applicability of this

framework extends beyond tree crown delineation and beyond the KH-9 satellite archive. The proposed multi-modal approach may be transferable to other land-cover mapping tasks and historical remote-sensing datasets, provided that imagery can be georeferenced and complementary temporal or multispectral information is available. As such, this work highlights a broader potential for integrating historical imagery into long-term Earth system analysis using modern deep learning techniques.

References

- Brandt, Martin, Clemens Romankiewicz, Raphael Spiekermann, and Cyrus Samimi. 2014. “Environmental change in time series – An interdisciplinary study in the Sahel of Mali and Senegal.” *Journal of Arid Environments* 105:52–63. ISSN: 0140-1963. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaridenv.2014.02.019>.
- Brandt, Martin, Compton J. Tucker, Ankit Kariryaa, Kjeld Rasmussen, Christin Abel, Jennifer Small, Jerome Chave, et al. 2020. “An unexpectedly large count of trees in the West African Sahara and Sahel” [in en]. *Nature* 587, no. 7832 (November): 78–82. ISSN: 0028-0836, 1476-4687.
- Dendoncker, Morgane, Martin Brandt, Kjeld Rasmussen, Simon Taugourdeau, Rasmus Fensholt, Compton J. Tucker, and Caroline Vincke. 2020. “50 years of woody vegetation changes in the Ferlo (Senegal) assessed by high-resolution imagery and field surveys” [in en]. *Regional Environmental Change* 20, no. 4 (November): 137. ISSN: 1436-378X. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-020-01724-4>.
- Ibrahem, Hatem, Ahmed Salem, and Hyun-Soo Kang. 2025. “Pixel shuffling is all you need: spatially aware convmixer for dense prediction tasks.” *Pattern Recognition* 158 (February): 111068. ISSN: 0031-3203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patcog.2024.111068>.
- Marzloff, Irene, Mario Kirchhoff, Robin Stephan, Manuel Seeger, Ali Aït Hssaine, and Johannes B. Ries. 2022. “Monitoring Dryland Trees With Remote Sensing. Part A: Beyond CORONA—Historical HEXAGON Satellite Imagery as a New Data Source for Mapping Open-Canopy Woodlands on the Tree Level.” Publisher: Frontiers, *Frontiers in Environmental Science* 10 (July 7, 2022). ISSN: 2296-665X, accessed September 10, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2022.896702>. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/environmental-science/articles/10.3389/fenvs.2022.896702/full>.
- NEON. 2026. *High-resolution orthorectified camera imagery (DP1.30010.001)* [in en]. <https://doi.org/10.48443/XV9V-1R95>. <https://data.neonscience.org/data-products/DP1.30010.001/RELEASE-2026>.
- Ronneberger, Olaf, Philipp Fischer, and Thomas Brox. 2015. *U-Net: Convolutional Networks for Biomedical Image Segmentation*, arXiv:1505.04597, May 18, 2015. Accessed January 30, 2026. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1505.04597>. arXiv: 1505.04597[cs]. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1505.04597>.

- Shahtahmassebi, Amir Reza, Minshi Liu, Longwei Li, JieXia Wu, Mingwei Zhao, Xi Chen, Ling Jiang, et al. 2023. “De-noised and contrast enhanced KH-9 HEXAGON mapping and panoramic camera images for urban research.” *Science of Remote Sensing* 7:100082. ISSN: 2666-0172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.srs.2023.100082>.
- Al-Shamayleh, Ahmad Sami, Mohammad Qatawneh, and Hany A. Elsalamony. 2025. “Advanced Retinal Lesion Segmentation via U-Net with Hybrid Focal–Dice Loss and Automated Ground Truth Generation” [in en]. *Algorithms* 18, no. 12 (December): 790. ISSN: 1999-4893. <https://doi.org/10.3390/a18120790>.
- Spiekermann, Raphael, Martin Brandt, and Cyrus Samimi. 2015. “Woody vegetation and land cover changes in the Sahel of Mali (1967–2011).” *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation* 34 (February): 113–121. ISSN: 1569-8432. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2014.08.007>.
- Stringer, L. C., A. J. Dougill, A. D. Thomas, D. V. Spracklen, S. Chesterman, C. Ifejika Speranza, H. Rueff, et al. 2012. “Challenges and opportunities in linking carbon sequestration, livelihoods and ecosystem service provision in drylands.” *Environmental Science & Policy* 19-20 (May 1, 2012): 121–135. ISSN: 1462-9011, accessed January 18, 2026. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2012.02.004>. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1462901112000342>.
- Wulder, Michael A., David P. Roy, Volker C. Radeloff, Thomas R. Loveland, Martha C. Anderson, David M. Johnson, Sean Healey, et al. 2022. “Fifty years of Landsat science and impacts.” *Remote Sensing of Environment* 280 (October): 113195. ISSN: 0034-4257. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2022.113195>.